

An Analysis of the Role of State Finance Commission in Revenue Sharing in Uttar Pradesh

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Abstract

This paper discusses the allocation of State Resources to Panchayati Raj Institutions (PRIs) and Urban Local Bodies (ULBs) at all three levels in the form of taxes, charges and levies collected by the State Government and Local Bodies. The Finance Commission was created under Article 280 to distribute revenue from the Central Government to the State Government through taxes and grants, but there was no provision for the devolution of revenue resources from the State Government to the Local Government. Local Bodies did not have sufficient resources to meet their expenses. The difference between the expenses of the Local Bodies and the revenue generated by them can be seen very easily. Local Bodies own revenue resources are not enough for their expenses like secondary and higher education, health and hospitals, highways and roads, police, housing, courts, public welfare etc. So, they depend on the revenue of the State Government for their expenses. To overcome these limitations and inadequacies and to give a constitutional status to Local Bodies, the Government of India made 3 institutions at the level of each State, The State Finance Commission is in one of them. The 73rd and 74th constitutional amendment gives protection and powers to Panchayati Raj Institutions (PRIs) and Urban Local Bodies (ULBs). This paper will also examine the performance of the State Finance Commission in revenue sharing between the State Government and Local Bodies. In this paper, we will also understand how the State Government devolve revenue resources with Local bodies through the provision of the State Finance Commission. This study will analyse the Uttar Pradesh state and its local bodies, revenue devolution including grants and taxes and assess revenue sources of Local Bodies.

Keywords

State Finance Commission, Local Government, Devolution, Panchayati Raj Institution, Municipalities, Uttar Pradesh.

Introduction

State Governments generate their revenue from two sources, the first is the revenue generated through sources such as SGST, Tax on liquor for human consumption, property tax, stamp duty, excise duty on petrol and diesel, electricity duty etc and the second source is the revenue transferred by Central Government to State Government on the recommendation of Finance Commission. These sources include shares in central taxes, general purpose grants, and specific purpose grants. As we all know, the condition of Local government in the past, but now the parameters are changing, and urbanisation is continuously growing especially the municipalities now they have sufficient economic power through which they are financially stable because of various supportive policies. Local Bodies also generate their revenue by own through user fees and property value etc and the revenue is transferred by the State Government and Central Government on the recommendation of the State Finance Commission. The government also make provision for Local Bodies to make them financially stable. In 1992 Central Government introduced two amendments in the constitution the first amendment was the 73rd amendment which was related to Panchayati Raj Institutions and the second was the 74th amendment which was related to Urban Local Bodies. Local self-government plays a crucial role in the delivery of social and economic services such as education, public health, housing, and urban development and in infrastructure like transport, power irrigation etc. Local Bodies are divided into two parts first is Rural Local Bodies (RLBs) or Panchayati Raj Institutions

(PRIs) in rural areas and the second is Urban Local Bodies (ULBs) or Municipalities in urban areas. Panchayati Raj Institutions (PRIs) are further divided into three types 1. Gram Panchayat (GP) at village level 2. Mandal or Block Panchayat or Anchalik Panchayat (AP) at block level 3. Zilla 4 Panchayat (ZP) at the district level and Municipalities are also divided into three types 1. The Municipal Committee covers a population of 10,000 to 25,000 people. 2. Municipal Council covers a population of 25000 to 1000000 people. 3. Municipal Corporation covers a population of more than 1 million people.

Structure of Local Government

Finance Commission

The President of India constituted the Finance Commission under Article 280 in the year 1951. The Purpose of the Finance Commission is to allocate certain revenue resources between the Central Government and State Government. The Finance Commission also define the fiscal relationship framework between the Central and State Governments. The Finance Commission give recommendations on the sharing of taxes between the Central and State Governments and transfers general purpose grants and specific purpose grants to the State Government.

The Finance Commission aims to reduce the fiscal imbalance between the Centre and the States (Vertical imbalance) and between the states (Horizontal imbalance). The Formula for sharing revenue is decided by the Finance Commission every 5 years. It promotes inclusiveness. So far, a total of 15 Finance Commissions have been set up, 14 Finance Commissions have submitted their reports, and the 15th Finance Commission is functioning. The 15th Finance Commission required Local Bodies Panchayati Raj Institutions (Rural Local Bodies) Gram Panchayat (At Village level) Block Panchayat (At block level) Zilla Panchayat (At district level) Municipalities (Urban Local Bodies) Municipal Corporation (Population more than 1 million) Municipal Council (Population 25000 to 1million) Municipal Committee (Population 10000 to 25000) 5 to submit two reports, first report with recommendation for the financial year 2020-21 and the final report with recommendations for the 2021-26 period.

State Finance Commission

The Finance Commission recommended the devolution of revenue sources between the Central Government and State Government through Tax and grants, but there was no provision for the devolution of revenue resources between the State Government and Local Government. Local Bodies did not have sufficient resources to meet their expenses. There is a huge difference between the expenses of the Local Bodies and the revenue generated by them. Local Bodies' revenue resources are not enough for their expenses, so they have to depend on the States. To provide revenue to Local Bodies, the Central Government constituted the 73rd and 74th amendments, the 73rd amendment is related to Panchayati Raj Institutions and the 74th Amendment is related to Municipalities. The constitution introduced Article 243-I (1) and Article 243-Y (1) to assess the financial situation of the Panchayati Raj Institutions and Municipalities. These articles recommend to the Governor every five years how the revenue resources should be divided between the State and the Panchayati Raj Institutions and Municipalities. This includes taxes, fees, tolls, duties, as well as grants from the State's consolidated fund. The 10th Finance Commission Recommended that all the States should have a State Finance Commission to recommend transfers to the Panchayat and Municipalities from the State Resources.

The 73rd and the 74th amendments of the Constitution of India provide – “243-I (1) The Governor of a State shall, as soon as may be within one year from the commencement of the Constitution (Seventy-third Amendment) Act, 1992 and thereafter at the expiration of

every fifth year, constitute a Finance Commission to review the financial position of the Panchayats and to make recommendations to the Governor as to:

I. the distribution between the State and the Panchayats of the net proceeds of the taxes, duties, tolls, and fees leviable by the State, which may be divided between them under this part and the allocation between the Panchayats at all levels of their respective shares of such proceeds.

II. the determination of the taxes, duties, tolls, and fees which may be assigned to, or appropriated by the Panchayats.

III. the grants-in-aid to the Panchayats from the Consolidated Fund of the State.

“243-Y (1) The Finance Commission constituted under article 243-I shall also review the financial position of the Municipalities and make recommendations to the Governor as to:

I. the distribution between the State and Municipalities of the net proceeds of the taxes, duties of the net proceeds of the taxes, duties, tolls and fees leviable by the State, which may be divided between them under this part and the allocation between the Municipalities at all levels of their respective shares of such proceeds.

II. The determination of the taxes, duties, tolls, and fees which may be assigned to, or appropriated by, the Municipalities.

III. The grants-in-aid to the Municipalities from the Consolidated Fund of the state (SFC Report) Here is the considerable divergence between the constitutional provisions regarding the setting up of the State Finance Commission by States and the working of SFCs on the ground. (SFC).

As per these provisions, it is the constitutional responsibility of the State Finance Commission (SFC) to determine the principles that should govern (a) the distribution between the state and the Local self-government(LSGs) of the net proceeds of taxes, duties, tolls and fees leviable by the state and the inter se allocation between different tiers of PRIs and ULBs; (b) the determination of taxes, duties, tolls and fees which may be assigned to or appropriated by the LSGs; and (c) the grants-in-aid from the Consolidated Funds of the state to LSGs. The SFC can also examine any other matter, which the Governor may refer to the commission in the interest of sound finances of the PRIs and the ULBs. Taking this constitutional provision into account, various states in India have constituted SFCs since the enactment of the 73rd Constitutional Amendment Act (Bishnu Prasad Mohapatra 2022).

Available information shows that 4 states have constituted their sixth SFC till date. 11 states have constituted their fifth SFC till date. Three states have constituted their fourth SFC and several states are still in their third and second SFCs. Uttar Pradesh has constituted the fifth State Finance Commission till now and Anand Mishra is the chairman of the fifth State Finance Commission of Uttar Pradesh.

Objective of study

The objectives for the present study on the topic “An Analyses the Role of the State Finance Commission in Revenue Sharing in Uttar Pradesh” are as follows:

1. To examine the status of the role of the State Finance Commission
2. To analyse the revenue resources of Local Government.
3. To analyse the devolution of State resources to Local Bodies.
4. To analyse the role and working of the State Finance Commission.

Review of Literature

Literature reviews are significant for the study as they are the platform of past research based on which present and future forecasts relating to any field or subject are carried out and help the researcher frame out the relevant scope for the study. These literature has been confined to the discussion of papers related to the State Finance Commission and fund devolution to Local Government, research articles and a thesis related to the study.

P Geetha Rani, (1999) studied the State Finance Commissions and Rural Local Bodies' devolution of resources. This paper attempts to critically review the recommendations of

five State Finance Commissions: Kerala, Rajasthan, Karnataka, Punjab, and West Bengal, on fiscal devolution in Panchayati Raj Institutions.

Om Prakash Mathur and Sandeep Thakur, (2004) studied India's Municipal Sector- A Study for the Twelfth Finance Commission (TFC). This study presents the fiscal performance of India's Municipal Sector, in the different states. This paper also explains the recommendation of the Finance Commission of states (SFCs) on devolution for municipalities. It additionally suggests choices for the Twelfth Finance Commission (TFC) on exactly how it may add to enhancing the funds together with the performance of communities.

P. K. Mohanty, B. M. Mishra et al., (2008) studied Municipal Finance in India: An Assessment. This study examines the functioning of Urban Local Bodies (ULBs) in India and analyses the reasons for their differential performance concerning fiscal parameters and the provision of public amenities by using data from 35 Metropolitan Municipal Corporations. In view of the findings of the study and international experience in this regard, the study has made recommendations for improving the urban financial system in India.

V. N. Alok, (2009) studied The Share of Local Governments in the Union Divisible Pool: An Option Before the 13th Finance Commission. This study indicates that local governments should consider sharing from the central divisible pool with the states. This will affect the fiscal devolution recommended to the states to correct the vertical imbalance. This study concluded that the 13th Finance Commission is not only able to play a positive role in fulfilling its mandate but also strengthen its fiscal capabilities for the empowerment of the citizens particularly the poor of the country.

Manish Gupta and Pinaki Chakraborty, (2019) studied The State Finance Commissions: How successful have they been in Empowering Local Governments? This paper reviews the State Finance Commission reports of the 25 states in India and examines the recommendation of SFCs and resource devolution from central to State and from State to Local Self-Government. This paper observed the huge variation in SFC devolution across States. This paper observed that despite the timelines of the legal provisions of the constitution, the State Finance Commission has been delayed in many States. States did not organise their SFCs periodically.

Abhijit Dutta, Madhabendra Sinha & Sudhansu Sekhar Mahapatra, (2021) studied a Critical Review of the Finances of Local Self Bodies of Sikkim in the Context of Finance Commission Provisions. This paper examines the extent to which Sikkim has been able to manage the Local self-government's resources and discusses the developments of the financial positions of these local bodies of Sikkim. Managing and sourcing the finances of the local bodies on the recommendations of the Fourteenth and Fifteenth Finance Commissions had always been a challenge for the states. Local bodies are one of the major instruments of the state to reach out to the welfare activities of the state.

Bishnu Prasad Mohapatra, (2022) studied the State Finance Commission and the Devolution of Funds to Panchayati Raj Institutions in Odisha, this article argues that the recommendation of the State Finance Commission supported the finances of rural local bodies and the devolution of state resources to Panchayati Raj Institutions has been increased year by year. This article concluded that the working of the State Finance Commission and its recommendations have supported PRIs in better financial positions and made them capable of delivering essential goods and services.

M. Gopinath Reddy and Bishnu Prasad Mohapatra, (2022) studied the Finances of Panchayats and the Status of Own Revenues in Telangana State: A Critique. This article argues that the revenue resources of panchayats are not enough for their expenses and remittances from the state and central governments are the two main sources of income for these bodies. this article

suggests the devolution of more taxes to PRIs by the SFC to strengthen their revenues and share at least 10% of the state's revenue to meet their expenses and to provide better goods and services in rural and urban areas of the states.

Research Gap

i. Though there have been many studies on the State Finance Commission in various states and their recommendations on allocation of funds to local governments but not much attention has been paid to the Uttar Pradesh State Finance Commission and revenue sharing between state and local bodies in Uttar Pradesh.

ii. The performance of the Uttar Pradesh State Finance Commission has not been examined or evaluated so far.

iii. The study is based on the Fourth State Finance Commission and covers a period from 2015 to 2020.

Methodology

Research methodology refers to the systematic process of planning conduct and analysing research. It comprises the theoretical framework techniques and methods for data collection and interpretation that are used to gather and interpret information. The methodology of Research ensures validity reliability and reproducibility of findings. It serves as a blueprint to guide researchers in their search for knowledge and understanding within a specific field or discipline. The Revenue Resources of Local Government is evaluated in the present study and This paper will use secondary data sources and analyse the role of State Finance Commission in revenue sharing between States and Local governments. For the study, this paper will analyse and collect data from State Finance Commission Reports of Uttar Pradesh State. The study also uses secondary data from budget documents, Economic Surveys, Finance Departments and the Ministry of Panchayati Raj's computerised database, reports, RBI reports on Municipalities, Uttar Pradesh Board for Development of Municipal Financial Resources, Report of the Comptroller and Auditor General of India (CAG) and existing studies. This study is based on the Fourth State Finance Commission and covers a period from 2015 to 2020.

Sources of State Government Revenue

There are mainly two ways of revenue resources of State Government, first is Own tax and non-tax revenue resources and second is share of states in central tax revenue and grants based on horizontal distribution criteria. States' revenue resources come from tax on income, tax on property and capital (land revenue, stamp, registration fee), Tax on commodity and services or SGST, tax on vehicle, entertainment tax etc.

Financial Sources of Local Government

The Uttar Pradesh Government aims to strengthen the finances of local bodies for promoting participatory democracy and grassroots empowerment, economic development at the grassroots levels and strengthening local governance. Strengthening the finances of the PRIs made them more capable of providing public services like healthcare, education, sanitation, and infrastructure. The revenue sources of local bodies are limited and could be classified into these categories.

1. Tax and non-tax revenue

The Uttar Pradesh Panchayat Raj Act, 1947 and the Uttar Pradesh Municipalities Act, 1916

authorize a village panchayat and municipalities to collect levies and collection of several taxes, tolls and fees. The tax and non-tax revenue resources of Local Government consist of revenue that comes from property tax, house tax, professional tax, vehicle tax, latrine tax, tax

on the agricultural land, pilgrim tax on animals, drainage tax, tax on works of public utility and market fees, charges like land registration duty, water charges, sewerage charges, trade licencing fees, sewerage connection charges etc.

2. Transfer from the Central Government

Revenue transfers from the Central Government through the Central Finance Commission are tax devolution, Local Government Grants, scheme-related grants, general purpose grants, specific purpose grants and other grants and Programme funds from Central Government schemes. UP Panchayats have received funds on the recommendation of the Central Finance Commission since 1996-97. Currently, as in SFC, funds received by Zilla Panchayats is 20%, kshetra panchayat's 10% and gram panchayat's 70%.

3. Transfer from State Government

Revenue transfers from State Government to local bodies are broadly divided into two parts, a) through State Finance Commission transfers and b) Programme funds from State Government schemes. Under the SFC transfers, there are three key sources,

namely, a) Devolution, b) Compensation and assignment of taxes, and c) Grant-in-aid. The devolved revenues are transfers from the state government to Panchayati Raj institutions as per the recommendation of the SFC for the implementation of various schemes and programmes (Mohapatra 2022). The assigned revenues are the assignment of taxes and fees from the state to local bodies and the grants-in-aid are part of both general and specific grants to local bodies (Mohapatra 2022).

4. Other Sources of Finance- Bonds, Loans, and borrowings.

Analysis

Analysis of the Uttar Pradesh’s Revenue Transfer to Local Bodies

Uttar Pradesh is the most populated state in India with over 200 million inhabitants. Uttar Pradesh is the fifth largest State in the country in terms of size and spans an area of 2.41 lakh square Kilometres. There are 59095 PRIs and 652 ULBs in the State. In RLBs, there are 75 Zilla panchayats (ZP), 826 Kshetra Panchayats (KP), 58194 Gram Panchayats (GP) and in ULBs there are 17 Municipal Corporations, 198 Municipal Councils and 437 Municipal Committees. SFC devolution depends on Some criteria and weights that were given Finance Commission every five years.

Table 1: Criteria and Weights for Allocation of Local Bodies Grants by the State Finance Commission

Parameter	Municipalities (Weight%)	Panchayat (Revenue%)
Population	40	50
Area	5	10
SC/ST	10	10
Per Capita Income	15	-
Establishment Comfort backwardness index	10	-
Integrated development backwardness index	20	30

Source: A Report Card of State Finance Commissions, Ministry of Panchayati Raj 2016

Table 2: Fund Allocated to Panchayati Raj Institutions under the Fourth and Fifth State Finance Commission

S.No.	District Name	No. of KP	No. of GP	2015-16 Fund Allocated to GP	2015-16 Fund Allocated to KP	2016-17 Fund Allocated to GP	2016-17 Fund Allocated to KP	2017-18 Fund Allocated to GP	2017-18 Fund Allocated to KP	2018-19 Fund Allocated to GP	2018-19 Fund Allocated to KP	2019-20 Fund Allocated to GP	2019-20 Fund Allocated to KP
1	Agra	15	695	2946.1	589.22	3510.64	702.12	3853.883	711.62	4027.637	818.545	4967.064	957.041
2	Aligarh	12	887	2799.8	559.96	3335.1	667.02	3380.21	676.04	3451.663	690.333	4090.359	818.072
3	Ambedkar Nagar	9	927	2342.62	468.52	2790.34	558.07	3063.167	660.59	3224.456	653.385	3950.399	642.766
4	Ameethi	13	682	2856.517	683.462	2998.06	599.61	3255.301	695.724	2770.735	554.147	3660.901	734.5
5	Amroha	6	801	2102.637	508.99	2223.69	444.74	2441.092	450.7	2382.619	476.524	3149.802	618.467
6	Auraiya	7	477	1768.39	353.68	2104.87	420.98	2132.67	426.53	2254.504	450.901	2684.216	536.843
7	Ayodhya	11	835	2445.02	661.077	2916.13	583.23	3202.049	690.87	3128.892	625.778	3726.054	745.211
8	Azamgarh	22	1871	4014.08	1073.508	4785.33	957.07	5252.352	970.36	5118.515	1023.703	6578.464	1325.331
9	Baghpat	6	245	2081.342	369.77	2198.58	439.72	2413.021	522.353	2351.243	470.249	2798.936	559.787
10	Bahraich	14	1054	3193.407	757.084	3156.29	631.26	3424.15	684.83	3632.549	726.51	4326.77	865.355
11	Ballia	17	948	3153.432	559.96	3115.86	623.17	3658.89	788.351	3557.986	711.597	4237.682	847.535
12	Balram	9	801	2002.47	400.49	2385.31	477.06	2418.2	483.64	2762.376	560.5	3392.549	722.979
13	Banda	8	470	1901.89	380.38	2264.96	452.99	2295.21	459.04	2428.532	485.706	2886.367	577.274
14	Barabanki	15	1166	3161.89	632.38	3716.09	743.22	4078.526	753.36	4299.206	870.771	4733.533	946.704
15	Bareilly	15	1193	2999.13	599.83	3573.45	714.69	3922.473	845.742	4147.489	839.811	5082.109	913.718
16	Basti	14	1235	2357.25	471.45	2794.36	558.88	3068.532	566.66	3000.38	600.076	3951.058	745.415
17	Bijnor	11	1128	3273.44	654.69	3896.55	779.31	3949.08	789.82	4180.623	836.125	4977.436	995.487
18	Badaun	15	1038	2649.84	529.97	3152.43	630.49	3461.392	639.14	3507.784	677.73	4035.612	807.122
19	Bulandshahr	16	951	3361.126	806.079	3554.41	710.88	3901.461	720.41	4048.015	762.804	4931.165	908.399
20	Chandauli	9	734	1973.21	394.64	2361.15	472.43	2391.84	478.37	2533.741	506.748	3017.359	658.598
21	Chitrakoot	5	335	1605.63	439.955	1784.49	356.9	1935	387	2044.555	408.911	2433.971	486.795
22	Deoria	16	1189	3085.301	539.48	3228.3	645.66	3272.59	764.197	3467.193	693.439	4114.367	822.872
23	Etah	8	576	1892.75	378.55	2251.16	450.23	2469.601	533.226	2412.918	482.584	3128.615	633.003
24	Etawah	8	471	2044.787	363.19	2161.47	432.29	2372.253	512.489	2444.123	402.728	2983.495	607.561
25	Farrukhabad	7	600	1900.06	380.01	2261.54	452.31	2481.519	458.16	2512.921	520.378	3060.814	642.194
26	Fatehpur	13	840	2540.12	508.02	3025.73	605.14	3320.912	715.929	3247.744	649.549	4301.613	916.757
27	Firozabad	9	569	2218.26	443.65	2465.88	493.18	2944.573	544.7	2808.046	561.609	3697.795	668.693
28	Gautam Buddha Nagar	4	88	1815.94	363.19	1739.73	347.95	1884.48	376.9	1855.83	371.166	2167.247	433.449
29	Ghaziabad	4	161	2507.983	446.58	2605.27	520.6	2484.1	496.82	2823.613	525.545	3458.331	703.602
30	Ghazipur	16	1237	3172.86	634.57	3530.55	706.11	4148.359	766.1	4369.046	886.668	5361.172	1132.132

